

The background is a dark blue gradient. Overlaid on this are several concentric, curved lines in various colors: orange, light purple, light blue, green, pink, and yellow. These lines are not perfectly circular but have a slight arc. Small, solid-colored circles of the same color as the lines are placed at various points along these arcs, creating a sense of movement or data points. The overall aesthetic is modern and digital.

DARIAH ERIC: Empowering
research communities with
digital methods to create,
connect and share knowledge
about culture and society.

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Foreword

2024 was a year of *celebration, expansion and innovation* for DARIAH. Our first decade as an ERIC was a series of firsts and successes across the DARIAH family. Our community expanded, with Sweden joining us as a new member country, and we welcomed new collaborations with our well-established and active Swedish colleagues.

We are more than looking forward to welcoming new member countries, as local communities and our partner organisations actively support and drive their efforts to join our shared mission.

The expansion of our network made us move even more swiftly towards new knowledge-sharing grounds. The launch of *Transformations*, the DARIAH Overlay Journal, enjoyed a great number of contributions from across Digital Humanities communities, confirming our vision that a trusted, non-commercial publishing platform would boost sustainability and reproducibility of research. But we made knowledge shareable and accessible in more than one way. In 2024 DARIAH published its first series of German-language training resources on DARIAH-Campus, released its first Glossary, and signed the Manifesto on Science as a Global Public Good (<https://doi.org/10.58079/v10e>).

2024 was a year of new *collaborations*. In February we launched ATRIUM, a project which we are proud to coordinate, and in which we aim to bridge leading research infrastructures in archaeology (ARIADNE), languages (CLARIN), and open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (OPERAS) and advance frontier knowledge in the Arts and Humanities - across disciplines, languages and media. A month later we joined the launch of OSCARS, a project which is consolidating past achievements of the Science Clusters into lasting interdisciplinary FAIR data services and working practices, and in September we participated in the much-anticipated public launch of ECHOES, the five-year project which is setting up the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH). Not least, we are continuing our work to highlight the role of DH within the EOSC, and we are contributing to the Data Space for Cultural Heritage, through our collaboration with Europeana, to encourage the use of cultural collections as data.

2024 was a year of *presence*. Our Annual Event, hosted in the hospitable NOVA FCSH, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, brought together almost 300 researchers from across 39 countries who discussed workflows in the Digital Humanities. The Theme Funding Call attracted over fifty applications, and we were delighted to support five projects which will be reflecting on the notion of Mistakes in DH.

2024, as any year, was one of *people*. Toma Tasovac, President of the Board of Directors, stepped down after six years of service. His vision, commitment and character brought DARIAH an unprecedented series of successes, and we are deeply grateful to him. As DARIAH continues to evolve and embrace new opportunities, we warmly welcome Susan Schreibman to the Board of Directors, confident that her leadership will guide us into the second decade of our journey.

Agiatis Benardou

President of the Board of Directors

Chris De Loof

Chair of the General Assembly

DARIAH in a Nutshell

The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) was established in 2006 to enhance and support digitally-enabled research and teaching across the arts and humanities. In 2014 the European Commission awarded DARIAH the status of a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). Two years later, DARIAH was awarded Landmark Status in the 2016 ESFRI Roadmap as a Research Infrastructure that reached its implementation phase and was considered a pan-European hub of scientific excellence. This year, DARIAH celebrated its first decade as an ERIC.

DARIAH develops, maintains and operates an infrastructure with 22 Member countries and several Cooperating Partners across ten non-member countries in Europe, the US and Egypt. By working with communities of practice, DARIAH brings together individual state-of-the-art digital arts and humanities activities and scales their results to a European level, enabling the transition to Open Science, and beyond to Open Innovation. It preserves, provides access to, and disseminates research that stems from these

collaborations and ensures that best practices, methodological and technical standards are followed.

We work across a wide range of arts and humanities research areas and with a diverse range of stakeholders, including those in academia and technologists, across the GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums) and not-for-profit sectors.

Activity Highlights

ATRIUM project kicks-off

At the beginning of the year, the European project ATRIUM – Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities kicked-off. Coordinated by DARIAH, this four-year project brings together 17 partners and 12 affiliated entities across 12 countries, exploiting and strengthening complementarities between four leading European infrastructures: DARIAH (digital arts and humanities), ARIADNE (archaeology), CLARIN (languages) and OPERAS (open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities). The project aims to improve workflows and access to the state-of-the-art services available to researchers across countries, languages, domains and media, with a particular focus on archaeological research.

January

Launch of *Transformations* – A DARIAH Journal

During the DARIAH Annual Event in Lisbon, DARIAH's first multilingual Diamond Open Access Journal *Transformations* was officially launched. The journal is an ongoing publication with thematic issues in Digital Humanities, humanities, social sciences, and the arts. It is particularly interested in the use of digital tools, methods, and resources in a reproducible approach and welcomes scientific contributions on collections of data, workflows and software analysis.

June

Annual Event 2024 in Lisbon

With more than 250 participants from 39 different countries, this year's edition was the largest annual event that DARIAH ever organised. The theme was *Workflows: Digital Methods for Reproducible Research Practices in the Arts and Humanities*. The event was held from 18-21 June at NOVA-FCSH, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, the National Coordinating Institution of DARIAH-Portugal, and hosted by the ROSSIO Infrastructure. The event kicked off with a day of internal DARIAH meetings and several pre-conference workshops, followed by three conference days with panels, papers, posters and demonstrations. Some of the event's highlights were the keynote lecture by Meredith Martin from the Centre for Digital Humanities at Princeton University on the topic of 'All Worked Up About Data' and the concluding celebratory panel reflecting on DARIAH's first decade.

April

Funding for six new DARIAH Working Group projects

Six new DARIAH Working Group (WG) projects began in Spring, funded by the WG Funding Call 2023-2025. With an overall budget of 40.000€, the selected projects focus on intangible and built heritage (ARCHETIPO WG), metadata-based research in art, humanities and social sciences (Bibliodata WG), supporting PhD students' training needs (Community Engagement WG), bridging gaps between industry and education for DH graduates (Joint project of Community Engagement and DH Course Registry WGs), creating, managing and archiving textual corpora in under-resourced languages (Joint project of Research Data Management and Multilingual DH WGs), and finally, performing arts in the digital realm (Theatralia WG). The WG Funding scheme is intended to support existing DARIAH WGs and to help them develop and share expertise and sustain existing tools and services.

July

Welcome to Sweden

We were delighted to welcome Sweden as DARIAH's latest full member! With each new member, DARIAH grows stronger, more diverse, and becomes better equipped to serve the digital needs of arts and humanities scholars across Europe. By joining DARIAH-EU, Sweden aims to link and align Swedish resources to international resources and provide Swedish and international scholars with mutual access to resources, tools, and training, while increasing the capacity for international collaboration.

Happy Birthday DARIAH!

2024 was a special year for DARIAH as it marked the tenth anniversary since becoming a European Research Infrastructure (ERIC). During its first decade, DARIAH was continuously growing and collaborating across borders, disciplines and methods, representing the voice of arts and humanities researchers. As we move on to DARIAH's second decade, we remain committed to fostering digital innovation and strengthening this multidisciplinary community in Europe and beyond. The first decade anniversary was marked with a series of events and activities which are highlighted in a dedicated section of this report.

August

Publication of the DARIAH Data Policy

In November, we were happy to publish the second version of the DARIAH Data Policy. This policy outlines the basic principles for managing and sharing research data within the DARIAH infrastructure and beyond. It promotes collaboration within the research community and throughout the entire research life cycle, from project planning and standardisation to publication and thus helps institutions and researchers to be more visible in the European Digital Arts and Humanities landscape. The DARIAH Data Policy can be read in conjunction with the DARIAH Service Policy that focuses on service offerings and provision across the network.

November

September

A new Director for DARIAH

Susan Schreiber, Professor of Digital Arts and Culture at the Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences of Maastricht University, joined the DARIAH Board of Directors in September. Schreiber has been involved in DARIAH in several roles since the preparatory phase of the infrastructure, as Co-Chair of the DARIAH Virtual Competency Centre on Research and Education, and as National Coordinator for Ireland. Schreiber brings with her decades of experience in digital scholarship and a deep commitment to advancing the digital humanities and we are grateful to have her on board.

December

Announcement of the 2024 DARIAH Theme Call winners

In December, the five winning projects of the bi-annual DARIAH Theme Call were announced, receiving an overall budget of around 45,000€. Launched in Summer, the 2024 edition of the DARIAH Theme call was dedicated to the topic of Mistakes and received the largest number of applications since the launch of this funding scheme in 2015. These very promising projects will explore the topic of mistakes as pathways for learning, discovery, and innovation. We are looking forward to showcasing their results at the 2026 Annual Report.

Celebrating DARIAH's first decade

"DARIAH's journey over the past decade has been one of continuous growth and collaboration – across borders, disciplines and methods. As we celebrate our first decade as an ERIC, we remain committed to fostering digital innovation and strengthening the community of arts and humanities scholars in Europe and beyond."

Toma Tasovac, Former President of the Board of Directors and current Strategic Advisor to the Board of Directors

August 6 2024 marked the tenth anniversary for DARIAH becoming a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). DARIAH's journey began in 2006 when four European institutions in digital humanities came together to ensure long-term sustainability. After securing funding through the European Commission's 7th Framework Programme, DARIAH transitioned to an ERIC in August 2014, with 15 founding members (Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Cyprus, Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Malta, The Netherlands, Slovenia and Serbia). DARIAH was later recognised as a pan-European hub of scientific excellence in the 2016 ESFRI Roadmap, and awarded Landmark Status. Over the past decade, DARIAH has grown through collaboration across disciplines and borders, aiming to foster digital innovation and support the community of arts and humanities scholars in Europe and beyond.

To mark this anniversary, a dedicated communications campaign was run across active DARIAH social media accounts (Twitter/X, LinkedIn, and Mastodon). A successful crowdsourcing campaign promoted via Twitter/X saw submissions from the DARIAH community that reflected key milestones, community memories, gatherings, and achievements from the past ten years. Headers across social media were adapted to this anniversary with the message "DARIAH10: Celebrating the first decade". This was also reflected in the rest of DARIAH's communication channels, such as the DARIAH website and the DARIAH newsletter. Regular updates were shared with the hashtag #DARIAH10 and photos recalling key moments and memories from the wider DARIAH community, including gatherings online during the pandemic, exciting developments in the digital humanities sphere, and contributions to research made by WGs, responses to Theme Calls. It was also special to observe the social element of the DARIAH community, reflected in the increasingly large number of submissions and registrations at Annual Events, contributions to DARIAH funding schemes and initiatives.

In a specially produced short video to mark the occasion, Directors past and present – Laurent Romary, Jennifer Edmond, Agiatis Benardou, Toma Tasovac, and Sally Chambers – reflected on the trajectory of DARIAH's first decade as an ERIC, culminating in some of the most successful years in DARIAH's history. Shorter clips were circulated on social media where directors reflected on the key moments and important contributions of DARIAH to establishing and maintaining a research infrastructure, generating engagement from the wider community and beyond.

At the DARIAH Annual Event 2024 in Lisbon, we were delighted to host a celebratory panel on the success of the first decade. This panel featured some of the current and past DARIAH Directors, who reflected on the history of DARIAH, especially in light of the success of 2024: it served as a hopeful and inspiring culmination of our annual gathering, as the Directors looked ahead to the next decade, outlining lessons learned, horizons widened, and goals and plans for the next ten years of being an established ERIC!

1. Nurturing and expanding DARIAH's Network

a. DARIAH at the national level

In 2024, the National Coordinators Committee (NCC) continued its work to advance DARIAH's missions on a national level. The NCC was particularly happy to welcome Sweden as a new Member, and supported them and other national consortia by continuing to share best practices during their monthly meetings. The NCC continued to oversee the integration of national services within the DARIAH ecosystem, taking advantage of interoperability between the SSH Open Marketplace and national platforms, or indeed, using the SSH Open Marketplace to host data on national services, for example, Text+ in Germany. The NCC

also shared information and compared strategies of engagement with the new paradigm of EOSC Nodes, a platform that primarily supports multi-disciplinary and multi-national research promoting the use of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and supplementary services in Europe and beyond.

Although at different stages in the construction of their national consortia, Sweden and France made particularly impressive progress in 2024. Their stories are featured below. We are also proud to feature the accomplishments of our members, which you can find on the map in the next pages.

Focus on Sweden

Koraljka Golub is Professor of Information Science at Linnaeus University, and she holds a doctorate in Information Theory from Lund University. She is the head of the iInstitute, Linnaeus University's iSchool and co-leader of Linnaeus University's Digital Humanities Centre. She is also coordinating Huminfra's work for DARIAH-SE, and through this, is the National Coordinator for Sweden.

Her teaching and research is in digital libraries and information retrieval, with particular focus on topics related to knowledge organisation. Golub is especially interested in the GLAM sector, its manifestations online, with how users find information and, as such, works with ontologies and the evolution of terms throughout time.

Could you introduce us to the role and the work of your consortium?

DARIAH-SE is the international manifestation of the national research programme called Huminfra, which aims to construct a humanities research infrastructure in Sweden. This consortium of 12 nodes across 11 universities is the result of two merged profiles that focus on the humanities labs (notably in Lund and Umea) and digital humanities research centers across the country. We also organise our activities around thematic areas of focus, ranging from the experimental humanities, quantitative approaches to humanities, the use of cutting-edge tools such as motion capture, in addition to more classic DH areas such as text analysis and database management.

Within the context of DARIAH, we wish to go beyond the 12 nodes that are officially part of the funded programme and bring in all Swedish humanities practitioners. As part of this effort, we are currently conducting a DH survey to build community beyond the Huminfra nodes.

What would you consider the 2024 highlights of DARIAH-SE?

2024 was a big year for Huminfra, as we finally joined DARIAH-EU on 1 July! This was the result of many years of hard work, going back to Cooperating Partnerships in 2016. The official launch event of DARIAH-SE in Växjö in December 2024 was an important moment, not only symbolically for all the work we've put in, but particularly as it brought members of the community together and helped them realize how important DARIAH membership is for Sweden. We were really happy to welcome Edward Gray, DARIAH's Officer for National Coordination, as our keynote speaker. Through our discussions, our community came to understand that DARIAH stands as a real motor to bring together Swedish DH researchers, including and beyond Huminfra.

Integration into the DARIAH ecosystem has been very rich, particularly with regards to exchanges about EOSC and Nodes, which brought more extensive collaborations with Huminfra's external partner, the Swedish National Data Service. We've integrated into other DARIAH bodies, including the NCC and WGs, including inviting Francesco Gelati, Chair of the Research Data Management WG to present at our DASH 2024 workshop. We've also taken advantage of DARIAH's services ecosystem, ensuring that Swedish resources are shared with the infrastructure, and that infrastructural services become available to Swedish researchers. From our earliest days, we've been all about building community beyond borders, and now that we're officially DARIAH Members, we can be even more effective.

Koraljka Golub

Focus on France

Nicolas Larrousse is Deputy Director of the French infrastructure dedicated to SSH, Huma-Num. His main focus is to supervise the activities of its Coordination of National and International User Communities (CONIC) department and as such he is involved in several European infrastructures and projects. Originally trained as an IT-specialist, Larrousse has had a long career that focuses on data interoperability issues and long term preservation of research data. A longtime DARIAHn, Larrousse was a member of the Joint Research Committee (JRC) before being named National Coordinator of DARIAH-FR in 2015. He has also served as both Vice-Chair (2019-2021) & Chair (2022) of the NCC.

Could you introduce us to the role and the work of your consortium?

From the outset of French involvement in the construction of DARIAH, we built a national consortium based on three national infrastructures which provided services to DARIAH: CCSD (HAL), OpenEdition (Calenda & Hypotheses blogs) and of course Huma-Num (mostly Web hosting).

As DARIAH services became more mature, in particular the SSH Open Marketplace, we were able to gradually involve more communities. For instance, a great deal of work has been done to give visibility to the production of what we call "Huma-Num's Consortia", which are working groups funded by Huma-Num. The principle behind a Consortium-HN is to bring together different types of actors (researchers, technical staff, librarians, engineers, etc.) coming from different institutions, with the aim of creating synergies. In return, a consortium is expected to provide guidelines of technological and/or scientific best practices, new standards, tools and training to help the community take all these into account.

It should be noted that the interest of national communities in DARIAH's activities was greatly enhanced by the participation of our European "DARIAHns" in the event organised to mark the 10th anniversary of Huma-Num. Following this event, DARIAH-FR expanded with diversified activities: from INHA which deals with cultural heritage to the BNF Datalab, and other partners involved in the valorisation of publications. We now have a broader community more actively involved in DARIAH activities, including the revival of a former DARIAH WG on Visual Media & Interactivity.

More broadly, we are in the process of coordinating French involvement in European infrastructures at national level through the creation of an exchange "forum" with IR* PROGEDO, the structure coordinating French participation in infrastructures in Social Sciences (CESSDA, ESS, SHARE). This takes as its inspiration the SSH Open Cluster at the European level.

What would you consider the 2024 highlights of DARIAH-FR?

2024 has been a busy year on the DARIAH-FR front, but I'd like to highlight two things that have been made possible by the DARIAH infrastructure.

Firstly, we were able to provide strong support for the national responses to the first call for proposals from the OSCARS project. Two of them were selected, which is a great success in the context of this highly competitive call for proposals.

Finally, we explored synergies and best practices with our colleagues in charge of national infrastructures in Italy, Germany and Switzerland. These exchanges are invaluable and feed into the development of our infrastructure at Huma-Num by discussing common challenges and potential solutions. These exchanges help feed into national projects such as the COMMONS project, which we presented at the last DARIAH Annual Event ([halshs-03881307v2](#)).

Nicolas Larrousse

Group picture of Huma-Num team, during Rencontres Huma-Num 2023 in Lyon.

b. DARIAH Cooperating Partnerships: An important milestone towards full adhesion

In 2024, DARIAH's Cooperating Partnership strategy continued to bear fruit by helping to build national research infrastructures in the SSH across Europe. While DARIAH lost two Cooperating Partner institutions, this was ultimately a positive development as Linnaeus University and Uppsala University became nodes in the Swedish national consortium as it became a full member of DARIAH. This demonstrates once again how important Cooperating Partnerships are to building national consortia to both policymakers and research communities.

DARIAH continued to actively engage with the network of Cooperating Partner institutions, integrating them more into the infrastructure and its activities. Most importantly, DARIAH participated in several events organised by Cooperating Partners in 2024, including three DARIAH Days and two meetings with ministry officials to help advance the process of obtaining National Membership in DARIAH. These events included a DARIAH Day at the University of Leeds (co-organised by all of our six UK partners), the Baltic DH Forum organised in Riga by the Institute for Literature, Folklore, and Art of the University of Latvia (ILFA), and an event in Iceland organised by the Centre for Digital Humanities and Arts. This last event took place alongside the DHNB 8th Annual Conference in Reykjavik in May, combined with the Baltic DH Forum in Riga, Latvia, these two events inspired colleagues in the Baltic countries to work towards adding DARIAH in their national roadmaps.

These meetings helped to introduce DARIAH more widely to their respective national research communities while communicating the benefits of joining and participating in the infrastructure as a member country, an institution or as individual researchers.

“ILFA’s partnership with DARIAH-EU was an important step in demonstrating Latvia’s commitment to becoming a full member of the DARIAH-EU. The most visible outcome of this collaboration was the Baltic DH Forum

– a community-driven event that not only brought together the Baltic DH community but also provided an opportunity to engage with policymakers from the Baltic countries in discussions on research infrastructures for humanities. Just as importantly, this partnership helped us secure five years of funding from the Ministry of Education and Science to support DARIAH-LV’s core activities, providing a much-needed foundation for the next stage of development.”

Sanita Reinsone, Scientific Coordinator of the Cooperating Partnership with the Institute for Literature, Folklore, and Art of the University of Latvia (ILFA)

DARIAH-EU also proudly renewed its partnerships with ELTE (HU), Helsinki University (FI), The Institute of Ethnology and Social Anthropology, Slovak Academy of Sciences (SK), the University of Aalto (FI), the National Library of Norway, and the University of Exeter (UK).

Baltic DH Forum 2024

2024 Highlights from our Member Countries

Ireland

Following a call from Research Ireland, Professor Jennifer Edmond was appointed as National Coordinator for Ireland while her institution, Trinity College Dublin, holds the role of the National Coordinating Institution. Nicole Basaraba was also appointed as Deputy National Coordinator and Joan Murphy as National Manager for DARIAH-Ireland.

Netherlands

An important highlight from the Netherlands in 2024 was the release of CLARIAH Tools which aims to support engineers in communicating their efforts using the CODEMETA standard. Furthermore, tools that meet a quality standard are displayed on INEO, a user-friendly platform that allows researchers to search, browse, find and select digital resources for their research in humanities and social sciences. Most excitingly, work is also under way to connect CLARIAH Tools directly to the SSH Open Marketplace.

Belgium

CLARIAH-VL and its project Paving the Way for an SSH Open Science Cloud for Flanders was funded by the Research Foundation Flanders (FWO) as an International Research Infrastructure (IRI) for an additional 4 years with a grant of more than 4.000.000€. Building on the achievements of the CLARIAH-VL Open Humanities Service Infrastructure (2018–2020) and CLARIAH-VL Advancing Open Humanities Service Infrastructure (2021–2024), this new phase will consolidate previous efforts.

France

One of the 2024 highlights for France was the implementation of a metadata quality control schema for the research data repository NAKALA. This schema relies on moderation from partners across France.

Switzerland

In 2024, DARIAH-CH undertook the preparatory work to secure funding for DARIAH-CH for the years 2025-2028 while all existing and new members confirmed their ongoing support for DARIAH-CH activities and action. These include national working groups on digital editions, infrastructure development and collaborations with GLAM. The DARIAH-CH partners also confirmed their ongoing involvement in the Swiss SSH Open Cluster (SSHOC-CH) to strengthen the SSH domain in Switzerland and to promote its interests.

Sweden

Sweden joined DARIAH as a full member in 2024. An event launching DARIAH-SE was held in December 2024 with Edward J. Gray as invited speaker from DARIAH-EU. The year was also marked with the uploading of the first Huminfra resources to DARIAH platforms, such as the DH Course Registry, DARIAH-Campus and the SSH Open Marketplace.

Poland

In 2024, the DARIAH-PL consortium received a grant from the National Recovery and Resilience Plan to develop a digital research infrastructure for the humanities and arts in Poland. Led by the Institute of Computer Science of the Polish Academy of Sciences, the project brings together 13 scientific institutions. The initiative aims to establish a national ecosystem for interdisciplinary research on archaeological materials and cultural heritage, providing advanced data processing services, research tools, and enhanced accessibility to digital resources. The total project value is PLN 71,835,475.87 (approximately 15.8 million €), of which PLN 57,637,042.87 (approximately 12.7 million €) is funded by the grant. The project kicked off on 1 April 2024 and is expected to run until 31 December 2025.

Germany

In 2024, the NFDI Association applied to become a national node in the EOSC Federation. The vision of NFDI is data as a common good for excellent research, organised by the scientific community in Germany.

Austria

In 2024, a Consortium-wide Funding Call for Strategic and Small Projects awarded six large-scale/strategic proposals with funding of approximately 310.000€ and 11 small-scale proposals with funding of approximately 60.000€. Another small-scale project call is scheduled for 2025. Overall, more than 70% of CLARIAH-AT's current funding is dedicated to community development projects.

Czech Republic

LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ's main repository on Linguistic Data and NLP tools expanded significantly in 2024 with 245 new items, resulting in an overall number of more than 2,500 items. Additionally at the National Library, several new contracts with partners led to an expanded network, with the Czech Digital Library now housing 357,000 documents from 13 digital libraries. The Czech Digital Library was also augmented by the first iteration of AI functionality, currently providing speech-to-text for querying, text to speech models for reading in a chosen language and text translation to a chosen language and page summaries using LLMs.

2024 Highlights from our Member Countries

Slovenia

In September 2024, DARIAH-SI co-organised the Language Technologies & Digital Humanities 2024 conference in Ljubljana, Slovenia. The conference has more than 20 years of tradition, and was thematically expanded in 2016 to include digital humanities. DARIAH-SI also organised a pre-congress event entitled “No More Document-Editing Nightmares: An Introduction to LaTeX for Humanities Scholars”, a hands-on tutorial serving as an introduction to LaTeX.

Croatia

In 2024, DARIAH-HR developed DARIAH Assistant, a mobile application designed for researchers in the humanities to easily record, archive, and organise field data. The app enables integration with digital repositories and will be freely available to the entire DARIAH-EU community and the wider public, fostering openness and the digital transformation of research practices.

Portugal

Two new projects were funded in 2024 by the Portuguese Science and Technology Foundation for building competences in research data management. The ROSSIO infrastructure and NOVA FCSH will be partners on these two projects. RE.DATA – Network for Research Data Management – is a consortium led by the University of Minho, in partnership with the University of Coimbra, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, ISCTE and Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, and NOVA.ID-RDM-CC. The Research Data Management Competence Center is a collaboration between all the schools at NOVA.

PORTUGAL

SPAIN

Spain

Two new partners joined CLARIAH-ES in 2024, Dialnet and SCAYLE. Dialnet is a bibliographic portal whose main purpose is to give greater visibility to Hispanic scientific literature. Primarily focused on the fields of Human, Legal and Social Sciences, Dialnet is a tool for searching for quality information. SCAYLE is Castilla y Leon’s Supercomputer center. Its principal activity is to improve research tasks at universities.

Italy

In 2024, DARIAH-IT advanced its work in the Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) project, a federation of the four Italian nodes of the SSH research infrastructures: DARIAH, CLARIN, E-RIHS, OPERAS. In February 2024, the General Meeting of H2IOSC was held in Rome while the first H2IOSC TNA call for DARIAH services opened in September 2024. The year ended with the organisation of the DARIAH Transversal Training Event, closing the H2IOSC Transversal Training series in December.

Bosnia and Herzegovina

In December, DARIAH-BiH organised a conference on Promoting digital infrastructure in the field of humanities and arts at the University of Sarajevo. This two-day conference featured the promotion of the DigiProHUMANE project and highlighted the work of DARIAH-BiH. The exchange between DARIAH representatives with the Ministry of Civil Affairs that followed the conference marked an important step in illuminating the potential for future collaboration in the digital humanities landscape with DARIAH-BiH, cultural heritage in Bosnia, and across WGs, European Projects, and DARIAH events.

Serbia

On May 26, the National Library of Serbia organised a workshop on Datafication in Libraries held by Milena Dobrova and DARIAH Director Sally Chambers. The workshop attracted 20 participants and it was the first activity that could indicate the launch of an innovative laboratory for the use and reuse of digital data in the National Library of Serbia.

Bulgaria

The innovations established by the Telamon Digital Epigraphy team and the AIAX front-end service and visualisation platform, one of Bulgaria's foremost contributions to DARIAH-EU, found new applications and significantly contributed to the broader development of digital epigraphy through the Prometheus Digital Epigraphy project—a new international initiative funded by the EU's Creative Europe Program.

Greece

In March 2024, the Athena Research Centre and the Academy of Athens organised the closing event of the flagship H.F.R.I. project entitled "The emerging landscape of digital work practices in the Humanities in the context of the European projects DARIAH and CLARIN" or, in short, Digital Landscape. The aim of the project was to analyse current digital practices in the humanities in Greece to support the consolidation of these practices by using the services of the national infrastructure APOLLONIS and to continue the cooperation with the European infrastructures DARIAH and CLARIN, for the benefit of the research communities in Greece and Europe.

Impact Case Study

A DARIAH Impact Case Study:

Building a Human Network for Sustainable Digital Humanities in Croatia

What did we do?

DARIAH-HR, one of the 15 founding countries of DARIAH-EU, built a national DH infrastructure by connecting over 40 institutions across Croatia. Through collaborative events, shared tools, and lasting partnerships, DARIAH-HR transformed fragmented efforts into an inclusive human network that empowers scholars, artists, and cultural professionals to engage with digital methods and reshape humanities scholarship.

Why did we do it?

DARIAH-HR developed a low-cost, community-driven infrastructure that addressed fragmented DH support and empowered Croatian scholars to shape digital transformation through trust, collaboration, and inclusivity. This model enables meaningful participation – nationally, regionally (through DARIAH WBH, and today SEE Hub) and across Europe – demonstrating how shared values can drive innovation beyond institutional size or resources.

Who did we do it for?

For researchers, artists, and GLAM professionals in Croatia and Southeast Europe seeking access to digital tools, collaborative opportunities, and sustainable knowledge infrastructures.

Overview

Although the Ruđer Bošković Institute (IRB) introduced Croatia into the preparatory phase of DARIAH as early as 2008, contributing technical expertise to the emerging European infrastructure, the Croatian Ministry of Science and Education took a different direction when establishing the national consortium. In 2013, recognising the strategic importance of embedding digital humanities within the national scholarly and cultural ecosystem, the Ministry appointed the Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research (IEF) – a small but pioneering humanities institution with a strong record in digitisation and repository development – as the Coordinating Institution of the emerging DARIAH-HR consortium. This marked a shift to a decentralised, humanities-based model focused on openness and collaboration.

Description of the Impact

Human-Centred Infrastructure

DARIAH-HR has consistently prioritised people over platforms, building not just infrastructure but a space for negotiation, learning, and transformation. From the outset, it connected diverse stakeholders – from universities to artists – around shared goals, mutual support, and inclusivity. Instead of institutional hierarchies, the consortium focused on shared ownership and tools that address real research needs.

This approach enabled smaller and under-resourced institutions to participate in shaping digital infrastructure and access tools they would otherwise lack the capacity to develop. Crucially, the model rests on a commitment to knowledge-sharing and accessibility: DARIAH-HR regularly organises workshops on digital humanities,

heritage, and the arts, with recordings freely available on its YouTube channel. Furthermore, DARIAH Info Days are held across Croatia and the region, often upon request, to ensure direct support and engagement. Beyond access to tools and knowledge, the DARIAH-HR has opened pathways to international collaboration: many researchers and institutions joined European projects and thematic networks for the first time, significantly expanding their visibility, mobility, and research relevance at the European level.

With DARIAH-HR's support, the Centre for Research in Glagolitic launched Croatia's first crowdsourcing campaigns for Glagolitic manuscript transliteration, enabling citizen participation and supporting related doctoral research. Marijana Tomić, Assistant Professor, University of Zadar, Croatia

Through collaboration with DARIAH-HR, the University of Rijeka co-organised the CLARC 2023 conference, developed tools for analysing cultural memory, and expanded its international research network. Benedikt Perak, Assistant Professor, University of Rijeka, Croatia

DARIAH-HR supported a cross-border project dedicated to the digital processing of rare manuscript materials, enabling regional collaboration and leading to the organisation of the first international DH conference in Osijek.

Tihomir Živić, Full Professor, J. J. Strossmayer University of Osijek

Surveys conducted during DARIAH-HR's community events show that its inclusive model encourages professional connections, supports knowledge sharing, and provides practical guidance. Users particularly appreciate personal support, training opportunities, and reliable communication channels. Instead of focusing on new tools, they highlight the value of regular contact, peer exchange, and events that build confidence in addressing digital challenges. Trust, collaboration, and continuity emerge as key elements of sustained engagement.

DARIAH-HR also maintains four larger annual events, each supporting a distinct but complementary aspect of community-building:

- **Digital Humanities & Heritage Conference** – international, interdisciplinary exchange; includes peer-reviewed proceedings;
- **DARIAH Day** – annual partner gathering; showcases work, strengthens collaboration;
- **DARIAH Picnic** – informal networking; shared insights, creative exchange, community building;
- **Baladria Summer School – intensive training; practical skills in digital methods; co-organised with DARIAH-EU.**

DARIAH-HR also contributed to addressing structural gaps in the European digital humanities landscape by co-founding two DARIAH working groups:

- **ELDAH** (Ethics and Legality in the Digital Arts and Humanities) – supporting researchers facing ethical and legal challenges in data handling;
- **Theatralia** – promoting the documentation and research of performing arts and integrating artistic practices into digital humanities frameworks.

DARIAH-HR TOOLS:

- **DH Register** – a national platform for creating and hosting registers relevant to humanities research and cultural institutions;
- **Tezaurus.hr** – a tool for creating and managing thesauri and controlled vocabularies;
- **Consent Form Wizard** – a GDPR-compliant multilingual tool conceptualised by DARIAH-HR and developed by CLARIAH-AT and ELDAH;
- **Mapping App** – for mapping and displaying data across sectors;
- **DARIAH Assistant** – lightweight, open-access mobile app for field research.

Looking Ahead: DARIAH-HR in the Next Decade

As DARIAH-HR moves forward, the consortium fosters essential dialogue on integrating artificial intelligence into digital humanities in ethically grounded, human-centred ways. This aligns with its long-standing ethos: building infrastructure not as an end in itself, but as a means of empowering researchers, supporting communities, and encouraging critical engagement with the digital realm.

One outcome of this dialogue is the DARIAH Assistant app, developed with community input to simplify field data collection and sharing. By easing access to open science, it embodies DARIAH's mission of inclusive, sustainable digital research. Successfully piloted in Croatia, the app has drawn interest for further use across the DARIAH network.

More broadly, over the past decade, DARIAH-HR has demonstrated that shaping sustainable digital research environments depends not only on technological vision, but on trust, meaningful partnerships, and shared responsibility. Its experience illustrates how the future of digital humanities in Europe may be built – collaboratively.

DARIAH Digital Humanities & Heritage 2024

c. Projects

ATRIUM: Advancing Frontier Research In the Arts and Humanities

Coordinated by DARIAH-EU

In 2024, DARIAH proudly assumed the role of coordinator for ATRIUM (Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities), a major new initiative funded under Horizon Europe launched on 1 January 2024. ATRIUM brings together four major European research infrastructures: DARIAH (arts and humanities), ARIADNE (archaeology), CLARIN (language technologies), and OPERAS (open scholarly communication for social sciences and humanities), with the shared goal of building stronger bridges between their services and communities. As coordinator, DARIAH leads the strategic and operational direction of the four-year project with 30 partners from 14 different countries and a budget of 10 million €.

2024 Highlights

- Leading Workflow Development for Digital Research**
 As Work Package Lead, DARIAH led the development of multi-step workflows for five key data types—text, image, 3D, sound, and geospatial data—with the aim of helping researchers apply digital methods more effectively. These workflows are integrated into the SSH Open Marketplace and their practical impact is demonstrated through real-world archaeological case studies.
- Peer Review Framework**
 To address the limitations of traditional peer review systems, DARIAH spearheaded efforts to design an evaluation framework for non-traditional research outputs such as datasets, workflows, training materials, and software. This initiative aims to support a more inclusive and equitable recognition of scholarly contributions within the Arts and Humanities.

- Transdisciplinary Interoperability**

DARIAH also collaborated with the Austrian Academy of Sciences to harmonise models, vocabularies, schemas, and ontologies across disciplines. This work enhances the connectivity and usability of services and data across research infrastructures, enabling more seamless collaboration.

- Events**

As the lead for events and communication within ATRIUM, DARIAH organised and contributed to a number of successful events in 2024. Highlights included the ATRIUM Workshop at the DARIAH Annual Event in Lisbon, the ATRIUM Researcher Forum in Poznan, and three targeted summer schools hosted in Lyon, Brno, and York.

“ATRIUM will not only improve access to tools and services across research infrastructures in Europe, but will also make a significant contribution to our understanding of research workflows. We want to make sure that our researchers know how to put things together, how to do complex things and how to share their results.”

Toma Tasovac, Principal Investigator for ATRIUM, Strategic Advisor to the DARIAH-EU Board of Directors

ATRIUM Kick-off, 01.02.24–02.02.2024, Berlin, Germany

DARIAH actively participates in several European projects funded by the European Commission to reinforce its strategy and empower research communities in the Arts and Humanities. In 2024, DARIAH was involved in 10 active projects, one of which is coordinated by DARIAH.

PALOMERA

The European funded project PALOMERA to support policy alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area (ERA), ended in December 2024. It delivered crucial insights on understanding why so few Open Access funder policies include books and provided actionable recommendations to change the current landscape. The project, coordinated by OPERAS, saw the participation of 14 organisations, including DARIAH.

The PALOMERA project collected data covering 39 ERA countries and all key stakeholder groups to gain a comprehensive understanding of the Open Access book policy landscape. Key results in this direction are the PALOMERA Knowledge Base (<https://knowledgebase.oabooks-toolkit.org>), which enables stakeholders to identify existing policies, the addition of a funder and policy section in the OAPEN OA Books Toolkit (<https://oabooks-toolkit.org/>) and the establishment of the OA book Funder Forum, as a platform in which policy making in relation to OA books can be discussed. In addition, an extensive set of actionable and aligned recommendations on Open Access (<https://zenodo.org/records/14330411>) was issued towards the end of the project.

The PALOMERA project has managed to increase the attention of scholarly books to key stakeholders and provided outcomes that will certainly shape the implementation of Open Access policies in the future.

ERIC FORUM II

This four-year initiative started in September 2023 with the aim of further structuring the cooperation between the ERICs and supporting the implementation of the ERICs' Policy in the ERA. The project develops shared practices, regulations and services to improve ERICs' sustainability and ensure compatibility with European political priorities.

One of the main pillars is dedicated to the implementation of a platform containing data and information about ERICs that will help stakeholders in visualising their impact and outcomes in the European research landscape. This effort is led by DARIAH which prepared the documentation needed to pave the way towards the platform's technical development. Through a desk study and interviews with key stakeholders, DARIAH was able to deliver a first set of user requirements and started a reflection over the challenges of collecting and curating data. Furthermore, DARIAH proposed recommendations towards a viable governance model for maintaining the platform after the end of the funding period.

OPERAS-PLUS

The OPERAS-PLUS project started in September 2022 to support the further development of the research infrastructure OPERAS (Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities) in its preparatory phase and on its way towards becoming an ERIC. DARIAH contributed to the project in two ways. Firstly it provided its expertise as an established ERIC and delivered two workshops to help OPERAS in designing their future governance model, according to their values, expectations and compliance with the formal requirements set by the European Commission. Secondly DARIAH addressed the problem of perceived prestige of innovative outputs, which are often not captured by the current assessment methods in academia. Following this, the OPERAS-PLUS project released in 2024 the *Guidelines on Publishing and Evaluating Innovative Outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities* (<https://zenodo.org/records/14221728>). This report analyses several case studies illustrating various aspects of innovation in scholarly communication and proposes concrete recommendations and criteria for recognising and rewarding innovative research outputs within research assessment frameworks.

CLS INFRA

The Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLS INFRA) project was funded from 2021 to 2025 with the aim to consolidate, integrate and further develop institutional, national and regional efforts to build shared and sustainable access to the high-quality data, tools and knowledge in the field of Computational Literary Studies. In the context of this project, DARIAH managed the transnational access (TNA) programme which offered the opportunity for scholars to obtain access in one of the project partner institutions across Europe to conduct funded research fellowship with a focus on Computational Literary Studies. In 2024 two calls were issued and 18 fellowships were awarded as a result.

In June 2024, a third Training School was organised by the Austrian Academy of Sciences and ACDH-CH in Vienna, welcoming 41 participants. The topic revolved around the use of programmable corpora in Computational Literary Studies. Training materials will be made available on DARIAH-Campus. Finally, DARIAH contributed to the online publication of a Toolkit for Data Sharing (https://clsinfra.io/toolkit_data_sharing/). Provided in a Wiki format, it offers readily comprehensible and easily implementable recommendations and templates organised along the lines of Research Data Life Cycle. It covers research good practices in the context of CLS corpora and data.

ECHOES

ECHOES (European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science) is a five-year initiative (from June 2024 to May 2029) to create the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) as a shared platform for heritage professionals and researchers to access data, innovative scientific and training resources and advanced digital tools co-developed by the heritage community according to their specific needs. ECHOES will create a digital environment that enables the digitisation of existing knowledge and the collaborative analysis of cultural heritage assets, facts, and phenomena. At the end of the project, ECHOES will deliver a single platform to integrate results of EU and national projects on Cultural Heritage. DARIAH will contribute throughout the project and lead the work packages dedicated to enhancing integration and collaboration. The aim is to ensure that ECHOES builds on and uses existing datasets, tools, and workflows and engages a diverse range of CH institutions through a dedicated Cascading Grants Programme.

AARC TREE

The AARC Technical Revision to Enhance Effectiveness (AARC TREE) project, kicked off in March 2024, will define common strategies for the development and deployment of AAls (Authentication and authorization infrastructure) in the pan European Research Infrastructures at large, to improve access and sharing of scientific resources and to improve interoperability among research infrastructure communities across the thematic areas.

The Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration (AARC) initiative was first launched in 2015 to address the increased need for federated access and for authentication and authorisation mechanisms by research infrastructures.

The main objectives of the project are the following: capture and analyse new Authentication and Authorisation interoperability requirements; define and validate new technical and policy guidelines to improve the integration of RIs across thematic areas;

expand the number of research communities that can implement the AARC guidelines by providing a validation environment and toolkits; bring RIs, e-Infrastructures and relevant stakeholders together to align strategies. DARIAH, together with CERN, co-leads the work package dedicated to the production of a compendium of AARC best practices.

OSCARS

The OSCARS project is a four-year project (from January 2024 to December 2027) that fosters the uptake of Open Science in Europe by bringing together ESFRI and other world-class research infrastructures organised in five "Science Clusters", ENVRI-FAIR (environmental science), EOSC-Life (life science), ESCAPE (astronomy and particle physics), PaNOSC (neutron and light source science) and SSHOC (social sciences and humanities). OSCARS will strengthen the role of the Science Clusters by developing Community-based Competence Centres and Composable Open Data and Analysis Services. The OSCARS project organises a series of open calls to support research communities to take up open science and foster the involvement of scientists in EOSC. The first call was launched in March 2024 and it was particularly successful, with 264 proposals submitted from 33 different countries and 59 funded projects. DARIAH leads the Work Package dedicated to identifying and providing Composable Open Data and Analysis Services (CODAS) accessible via Virtual Research Environments (VREs) in EOSC. CODAS are service catalogues, data hubs and analysis platforms at varying levels of maturity, developed by the Science Clusters. Ultimately, these tasks will foster the alignments of practices in scientific data analysis.

DS4CH

The common European data space for cultural heritage project, funded by the European Commission, supports the digital transformation of Europe's cultural sector. It allows cultural heritage institutions across Europe to share digitised cultural heritage content, with high-quality metadata, including 3D. It also promotes the reuse of digitised cultural heritage among various audiences, creating value for the economy and society. The project, which kicked off in September 2022, facilitates capacity building in the cultural heritage sector, enables easy access to cultural content and creates digital opportunities for the public.

In the context of this project, DARIAH produced several assets, including a workflow to publish Collections as Data (available on the SSH Open Marketplace); introductory courses on Europeana APIs and Cultural Heritage Data Modelling (available through DARIAH-Campus); and an online webinar in November 2024, with 158 registrations, focusing on DARIAH-Campus courses on digital cultural heritage.

d. DARIAH and the EOSC: A new chapter for EOSC

With the EOSC Future project drawing to a close at the end of March 2024, to mark the occasion, DARIAH co-organised together with LifeWatch ERIC, the final workshop which took place from 5-7 March 2024 in Barcelona. The workshop, entitled *“Accelerating Open Science in EOSC: Collaborative interfaces between scientific domains and disciplines”*, welcomed researchers and research infrastructure experts from across the disciplines to consolidate the work undertaken in EOSC Future and to prepare the path ahead. With a focus on exploring how researchers in all domains are progressively working with more data and complex workflows using Open Science methods, the workshop showcased the benefits of working at the ‘collaborative interfaces’ between disciplines. The end of the EOSC Future project, signalled a turning point for EOSC towards the development of the EOSC EU Node which was officially launched at the EOSC Symposium 2024 in Berlin in October 2024 (<https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>).

Summer 2024 paved the way for the new chapter of the EOSC story, with the first steps being taken towards transforming EOSC into a Federation. DARIAH was keen to contribute to the build-up of the EOSC Federation. DARIAH, along with CLARIN and CESSDA, were among the 121 respondents of a questionnaire carried out in Summer 2024. In its response, DARIAH clearly stated its intention to offer DARIAH resources, such as those that can be explored in the DARIAH Tools & Services catalogue, through a future EOSC Node of the EOSC Federation. DARIAH also noted the importance of onboarding resources to the SSH Open Marketplace, co-managed by DARIAH, CESSDA and CLARIN.

Additionally, DARIAH stressed that at this stage, it does not anticipate the establishment of a standalone ‘DARIAH Node’, but would prefer to develop an EOSC Thematic Node for the Social Sciences and Humanities by joining forces with its sister ESFRI Research Infrastructures, such as CESSDA and CLARIN, via the SSHOC Cluster. This way DARIAH takes responsibility to foster networking in the SSH domain. This also includes a close collaboration with Cultural Heritage initiatives, such as the common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage and the Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH). Finally, DARIAH contributed to the writing team of the EOSC Federation Handbook (<https://eosc.eu/eosc-federation-handbook/>), which is intended to provide an overview of the organisation and operational structure, as well as the technical characteristics of the EOSC Federation. This work concluded in DARIAH’s participation in a related panel at the EOSC Symposium in October 2024.

Other EOSC-related activities in 2024 included DARIAH’s work in the OSCARS Project, and in particular, co-organising the OSCARS Consolidation and Terminology Workshop that took place from 30th September - 2nd October 2024 at the DESY Accelerator Centre in Hamburg, Germany. The event brought together colleagues from all five Science Clusters to discuss their catalogues of services and data sources and to identify how to make them into composable workflows using open science methods.

Finally, our EOSC-related activities in 2024 ended on a policy related note with the organisation of a workshop *“Coordinating the European Research Area: the role of ERICs and national stakeholders – strengthening the Social Sciences and Humanities”*, hosted by the Dutch Research Council (NWO) organised in conjunction with the DARIAH General Assembly and the National Coordinators meeting in November 2024. The workshop shed light on implications of the development of pan-European initiatives such as the ESFRI Forum and the EOSC for national research policies. Stakeholders in the Dutch research infrastructure landscape for the Social Sciences and Humanities together with international experts discussed the future of RIs including EOSC.

EOSC Symposium 2024, photographs by Andrew Grauman.

Impact Case Study

A DARIAH Impact Case Study:

Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLS INFRA)

What did we do?

Computational Literary Studies (CLS) is a new area of studies, established partly due to the activities of the CLS INFRA project (2021-2025). The participants of CLS INFRA conducted training activities, wrote field studies and literature reviews and offered fellowship opportunities to ECRs, in order to support the recognition of CLS as a field of study at an international level.

Why did we do it?

The key motivation for the activities mentioned above was to support the consolidation of Computational Literary Studies as a distinct subfield within the Digital Humanities. The primary kind of impact we were looking for was, in that sense, to develop networks and collaborations. Indirectly, we also aimed to foster research excellence.

Who did we do it for?

The target audience was the community of practitioners of computational literary studies research in Europe and beyond, but also traditional literary scholars, as well as computational linguists.

Overview

The CLS INFRA (Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure) project is aimed at transforming how European literary heritage was accessed, studied, and shared by consolidating fragmented resources and building a sustainable research infrastructure for computational literary studies (CLS). Recognising that literature serves as a rich archive of human values, norms, and creativity, the project was founded on the premise that literary texts are not only cultural artefacts but also valuable sources of data. It responded to a growing community of researchers using computational methods to investigate Europe's multilingual and interconnected literary history.

At its core, the project sought to provide unified and easy access to high-quality literary data and analytical tools. It focused particularly on narrative prose, poetry, and drama, aiming to make data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) and compliant with legal and technical standards. The participation of key infrastructures like DARIAH and CLARIN ensured that the project's results were not only widely adopted but also sustainable within broader European digital research environments.

CLS INFRA placed a strong emphasis on community engagement. It mapped user requirements within the CLS community and designed API-enabled "Programmable Corpora" to bridge the gap between user needs and the fragmented reality of existing resources. The project developed and optimised Natural Language Processing tools, workflows, and training materials to support both new and experienced users in applying computational methods to literary research.

Through a series of collaborative initiatives, including training schools, policy engagement, and shared resource development, CLS INFRA fostered networks of scholarly exchange and institutional cooperation. Its outputs included integrated tools, multilingual corpora, documentation toolkits, policy briefs, and explainer videos, all designed to advance the digital transformation of literary studies. Ultimately, CLS INFRA created the foundations for a cohesive, inclusive, and technologically advanced research ecosystem in the field of CLS. By addressing infrastructural fragmentation and promoting methodological innovation, the project made a lasting contribution to consolidate the newly emerged field of Computational Literary Studies.

Description of the Impact

The foundation, in 2022, of the Journal of Computational Literary Studies (JCLS, <https://jcls.io>) and of the annual Conference of Computational Literary Studies (CCLS) connected to the journal, with the support of CLS INFRA, has been a major signal of impact. In the first years of their existence, JCLS and CCLS have already developed into pan-European and international venues for presentation and publication of research in CLS.

The impact of the network represented by CLS INFRA is clearly visible in CCLS and JCLS. Many of the presenters and authors are in some way affiliated with CLS INFRA or its predecessor project, the COST Action "Distant Reading for European Literary History". Also, the broad representation of authors from a wide range of countries and distinct analysis undertaken within literary texts in a wide range of languages, shows the influence of the European network.

Beyond the conference and journal, the rise of Computational Literary Studies can also be seen in some quantitative indicators. For example, the number of articles mentioning the phrase "Computational Literary Studies" in Google Scholar has steadily risen over the years, from 32 in 2019 to 188 in 2024. Google Ngram data for the time period 2003 to 2022 shows that the phrase "Computational Literary Studies" has been on the rise since approximately 2016, and has overtaken the (broader) phrase "Computational Humanities" after 2019.

To some extent independently, but still in connection to CLS INFRA and under the inspiration of individuals who became central to CLS INFRA, a few other initiatives

were initiated at roughly the same time. These included the German Research Foundation's priority programme on Computational Literary Studies, as well as ADHO's Special Interest Group: Digital Literary Studies (SIG DLS), or Federation of Stylometry Labs (FoSL), in addition to a few research projects which were later referred to as CLS, funded by several national research agencies (DFG, NCN, FWO etc.). The culmination of these related initiatives was the EU project CLS INFRA, that at its core aimed at consolidating the resources, tools, methods, people, and training into a unified field of CLS.

Part of the objective of this research was to address the fragmented landscape of (literary) datasets. While a decade ago, researchers routinely used their own tailored collections of, say, a few dozen novels, acquired from various sources, today's landscape is substantially different, with several high-quality corpora of literary texts, usually accompanied with well-curated metadata. Due to the CLS INFRA's immediate predecessor – the COST Action "Distant Reading" (2017-2022) – researchers can work with a rich corpus of European novels, whereas CLS INFRA supported and popularized the corpus DraCor, containing hundreds of dramatic texts across several European traditions. These two resources alone led to several papers that pioneered and further developed the field of CLS.

While these developments have certainly not been driven by CLS INFRA alone (other developments include, for example, the German Research Foundation's priority programme on Computational Literary Studies), the pan-European nature of this development clearly shows CLS INFRA's significant contribution to this development.

Comparative Analysis based on the Google Books Ngram Viewer for the time period 2003 to 2022 at <https://books.google.com/ngrams/>.

2. Activities and Results

a. Working Groups

The DARIAH Working Groups (WG) reflect the diverse and rich landscape of the interdisciplinary research undertaken in the digital arts and humanities more generally, and in particular within the DARIAH infrastructure. In 2024, DARIAH counted 14 active WGs. This includes a new WG, DHwiki, as well as a re-launch of the Visual Media and Interactivity WG.

Throughout 2024, members of DARIAH WGs have contributed immensely to the digital humanities landscape in the form of software, tools, thesauri, workshops, and publications. Below are highlights of some of their 2024 activities:

- The **ARCHitectural HERitage Thesaurus through Integrated digital Procedures and Open data (ARCHETIPO)** WG strengthened its interdisciplinary network through key activities such as the organisation of the Poggioreale Workshop, where experts and students collaborated on innovative digital heritage documentation strategies, and the Training Camp, which provided hands-on experience in HBIM, GIS, and photogrammetry for abandoned historical settlements.
- 2024 was a year of intense and productive data sprints for the **Women Writers in History** WG, who have been migrating data to their upcoming VRE, **SHEWROTE** (Studying Historical Early Women's Reception: Oeuvres, Texts, Engagements).
- **Digital Practices for the Study of Urban Heritage (UDigiSH)** WG researchers have contributed to the recently inaugurated exhibition "**Cyprus Insula: History-Memory-Reality**", which will run from 4 July 2024 – 30 June 2025 at the Bank of Cyprus Cultural Foundation. This installation is part of the WG's multidisciplinary and holistic effort to preserve the modern architectural heritage of the Nicosia International Airport.
- The **Bibliographical Data** WG published a collective paper, "*Open Bibliographical Data Workflows and the Multilinguality Challenge*" in the Journal of Open Humanities Data, which is an output of the DARIAH Theme Project 2022-2024 (DOI: [10.5334/johd.190](https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.190)).
- The **Digital Humanities Course Registry** WG hosted a workshop on Digital Humanities & Industry at the 2024 DARIAH Annual Event and continued to grow their international membership of national moderators.
- The **Digital Numismatics** WG participated in a variety of conferences, workshops, and meetings throughout the year, and have produced two additional resources – online portals covering The Epigraphy of Monetary Economy in Anatolia, c. 700-30 BCE and site finds of coins of the same period from Anatolia.
- The **Community Engagement** WG leveraged a DARIAH WG grant to build upon their 2023 survey into the training needs of early career researchers and, in 2024, delivered a series of online and in-person workshops. These workshops introduced DARIAH services such as Campus and the SSH Open Marketplace, as well as specific tools such as OpenRefine. They welcomed almost 80 participants overall, both in person and online.

Working Groups Activities: 2024 at a glance

2024 was also a fulfilling year for Working Group collaborative efforts:

- With support from the DARIAH WG Funding Call for 2023-2025, awarded for their proposal “**Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages**,” both the **Multilingual DH** WG and the **Research Data Management** WG organised several workshops and conferences that in turn yielded increased memberships and related publications.
- Both the **#dariahTeach** and **Ethics and Legality in the Digital Arts and Humanities (ELDAH)** WGs launched the Social Justice in DH course, a collective effort of Social Justice ‘case-owners’ contributing to the open, case-based curriculum of the course.
- The **Thesaurus Maintenance** WG and the **THEATRAlIA** WG collaborated on an online workshop, “**Performing Arts terminology within the BBT model**.” The Backbone Thesaurus is an incredibly important resource that continues to be maintained and curated by the **Thesaurus Maintenance** WG, while the **THEATRAlIA** WG continues to build upon their roadmap for establishing the general structure of digital description languages for the performing arts.

Focus on the new Working Group: DHwiki

In a general context where GLAM and research data become open and FAIR, an increasing number of projects rely on deploying software provided by the Wikimedia Foundation and related initiatives. As such, public infrastructures, such as those run by Wikimedia, emerge as important or even central repositories of cultural knowledge. Hence we are witnessing more and more fruitful collaboration between DH researchers, GLAM institutions, and members of the Wikimedia movement. This WG is a bridge between these three groups, and it understands its work as a contribution towards Open Science and the Commons.

More specifically, in the context of DARIAH an increasing number of community members is contributing to or using Wikidata for different purposes. In addition, Wikibase has recently emerged as a software solution chosen for a wide range of organisations and projects of different kinds and scale. This WG is a space for discussion and dissemination of use case experiences and best practices around Wikibase and Wikidata both in a DH context, as well as for contributions to further develop the Wikibase software and related tools.

The WG maintains a Wikibase instance and a Zotero group, and aims at being present and available to the community in different fora.

WG DHwiki is chaired by David Lindemann (UPV/EHU University of the Basque Country and Wikimedia Basque Country, chair), a Wikibase user with a background in lexicography, corpus linguistics, and bibliographical data, and Gustavo Candela (University of Alicante and Wikimedia Spain, co-chair), a DH researcher working on collections as data, Wikidata, GLAM and digital libraries. Other members of the founding group are Christos Varvantakis, a social anthropologist working as Partner Manager at Wikimedia Deutschland, and Ismael Olea (Wikimedia Spain), developer, maintainer and trainer in GLAMwiki-related services.

David Lindemann

Gustavo Candela

b. Education and Training

DARIAH-Campus

DARIAH-Campus (<https://campus.dariah.eu>) was launched in 2019 to be the central resource within DARIAH for free and open training resources on a broad range of topics related to digital arts and humanities. It serves two functions: it is a **discovery framework** for training resources that exist within the DARIAH eco-system and; it is a **hosting platform** for training resources created by DARIAH-affiliated individuals, institutions and projects.

2024 was a very successful year for DARIAH-Campus in terms of the number of resources published to the site. Over a 12 month period, a total of 50 new resources were published on a variety of topics. The University of Brighton published a collection of six resources for digital heritage practitioners, focussing on issues of ethics and data management as well as techniques such as photogrammetry that can be used on a day-to-day basis. The University of Vienna also published a collection of resources focussing on the practicalities of AI prompt engineering, geospatial analysis, and databases in Humanities research.

In 2024, the DARIAH-Campus site received 6574 visits, and welcomed 1,097 people, 666 of whom were new users to the site. As in 2023, there was a further increase in referrals coming from social media, showing a trend in increase in traffic coming to DARIAH-Campus via the social media links on platforms such as YouTube, Twitter/X, and LinkedIn. This is explored further in relation to the #TrainingTuesdays campaign below.

Of the visitors to the DARIAH-Campus site, the overwhelming majority came from Europe. The top five countries in terms of number of users visiting the site were Spain, UK, Austria, Italy and Germany. Visits

also came from people in the United States, as well as Australia, India and South Africa, further indicating the international appeal of resources on DARIAH-Campus.

DARIAH-Campus Outreach

In May 2024, DARIAH-Campus was represented by Dr. Vicky Garnett (Training and Education Officer) at the DH Nordic and Baltic conference held in Reykjavik, Iceland, as part of a workshop alongside other training and learning resource providers. The workshop, led by the University of Luxembourg, focussed on the current state of training and learning resource provision, and what each organisation represented on the panel has done in terms of intervention and their future plans.

In December 2024, Vicky Garnett was invited along with other members of the DARIAH-EU team to present at the "H2IOSC Café – Presenting DARIAH" event organised by DARIAH-IT. This presentation re-introduced members of the DARIAH-IT community to the opportunities of publishing in DARIAH-Campus, as well as in reusing the materials and resources it has to offer.

Training Tuesday Campaign

The Training Tuesday campaign entered its fifth year in 2024, having launched in 2020. This was also the first full year of publishing posts to both Twitter/X and LinkedIn. While the hashtag #TrainingTuesday is by no means exclusive to DARIAH, it does represent a means of disseminating training materials to different audiences. The resources from Training Tuesday are also highlighted in the monthly DARIAH Newsletter, showcasing the resources that were featured in that month's campaign, thus adding a further means of promotion for both DARIAH-Campus and the individual training resources.

Infographic map of Europe showing level of users of DARIAH-Campus in 2024, indicated by shades of green. The darker the shade, the more users in that country. The darkest greens are seen in Spain, UK, Italy and Germany.

Engagement with posts on Twitter/X increased in 2024, continuing the upward trend since 2022 in engagement with our communities in relation to training (see table 1 below). Reviewing the past five years of the campaign reflects wider societal changes. While the COVID-19 pandemic saw huge engagement with the resources highlighted through social media, since 2022 there has been a steady re-growth of this audience as people returned to in-person learning environments.

2024 is the first year we have gathered statistics from LinkedIn, so this creates a baseline from which we can determine success on that platform. On this social media platform, performance is indicated through likes and reposts. In 2024, posts from the #TrainingTuesday campaign were 'liked' a total of 212 times, and reposted 41 times.

In 2024, the top ten posts in the #TrainingTuesday that attracted the most engagement on Twitter/X featured resources from four main sources: Programming Historian, Europeana, the University of Brighton and the CLS INFRA project. Of these most-engaged resources, the topics included cultural heritage, maps and spatial analysis, and research methods. Over on LinkedIn, the top ten most engaged posts once again featured contributions from Europeana, Programming Historian and the University of Brighton, but it also included resources from other universities such as the University of Vienna and the University of Reykjavik. Topics most favoured in LinkedIn included cultural heritage as seen on Twitter/X, but also included issues around ethics, AI prompt engineering, corpus tools and structured data.

Friday Frontiers

The 2024 Friday Frontiers series ran successfully in Spring and in Autumn/Winter. Following DARIAH's strategy of engaging and ensuring more open resources for training events and materials beyond the DARIAH community, Friday Frontiers was once again a training series open to the public.

The Spring series in 2024 kicked off in March with a presentation from Bernard Pochet about the best practices in 'Diamond' publication and Open Science at the University of Liège. In April, Pétur Húni Björnsson from the University of Reykjavik discussed his research to develop the Historical Farm and People Registry as the basis of a reliable infrastructure for research involving data on people and places in Iceland from 1703 to 1920. And in May, Andrew Sneddon and Victoria McCollum from the University of Ulster joined us fresh from their travels back from an awards ceremony in the USA to tell us about their recent 'Witches of Islandmagee' exhibition.

In the Autumn/Winter series we began in October by welcoming the team from the Sloane Lab, Dr. Andreas Vlachidis (University College London), Prof. Dr. Julianne Nyhan (University College London/TU Darmstadt), Dr. Andrew Flinn (University College London), and Dr. Alda Terracciano (University College London) to talk about the processes behind setting up the Sloane Lab, as well as some of the outreach programmes and ethical community engagement and co-design practices they have initiated. In November, Prof. Susan Schreibman and Dr. Costas Papadopoulos (University of Maastricht) gave an insight into the 3DPure project, incorporating 3D models of historical re-enactments to give new perspectives on the past. And finally in December, Prof. Jennifer Edmond and Dr. Eleonora Lima (Trinity College Dublin) from The Knowledge Technologies for Democracy (KT4D) project presented and led a discussion on how democracy and civic participation can be better facilitated in the face of rapidly changing knowledge technologies – namely Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Big Data.

Overall in 2024, the Friday Frontiers webinars attracted over 240 registrations, with 140 people attending during the live events. All these webinars were published on DARIAH-Campus following the end of the series and are available and open to the public.

Table 1: Twitter/X #TrainingTuesday campaign statistics 2020-2024

Year	Total tweets	Impressions	Total engagements	Likes	Click throughs	Retweets
2020	49	150,135	2,469	499	567	350
2021	45	81,701	1,223	320	296	205
2022	30	20,610	527	148	120	75
2023	33	32,831	1,144	353	379	136
2024	36	31,531	1,508	414	404	181

Impact Case Study

A DARIAH Impact Case Study: Helsinki Digital Humanities Hackathon

What did we do?

The Helsinki Digital Humanities Hackathon (DHH) began 10 years ago as an experiment that developed into an annual experience to develop an interdisciplinary research project from start to finish within the span of 10 days. It is organised as a master's level university course and an international summer school every year.

Why did we do it?

A decade ago it seemed that there was a gap between humanities, DH and CS. We thought a new type of hackathon would be an ideal bridge. DHH gives the opportunity to test abstract knowledge against complex real-life problems. Bridging disciplinary boundaries is the core of DHH: data scientists and humanities scholars join forces to tackle complex research questions together.

Who did we do it for?

From the beginning, we have targeted researchers and students from various backgrounds, including humanities, social sciences, computer science and data science, who wish to collaborate on an interdisciplinary research project.

Overview

The Helsinki Digital Humanities Hackathon has been running yearly since 2015*, starting as a five-credit master's level course as part of the Digital Humanities minor subject at the University of Helsinki. It subsequently became part of the Digital Humanities MA study track. The course is also offered separately as part of the data science master's program and at Aalto University for students of computer science. Since 2019, the hackathon has been organised as a DARIAH and CLARIN summer school, welcoming participants from all over Europe and beyond.

For ten days, participants work in groups organised around predefined themes. Each interdisciplinary team develops a project from start to finish, fusing computational strategies with humanistic perspectives. Working together, they formulate research questions with respect to particular data sets, develop and apply methods and tools to answer them and present the work at the end of the hackathon. This collaboration demonstrates how theoretical and interpretive skills and computation strengthen each other. During the hackathon, students acquire skills that will be useful to them regardless of whether they are thinking about an academic career or aiming to find a job outside academia.

** In the year 2020 the hackathon was not organised due to the COVID-19 pandemic.*

Description of the Impact

Helsinki Digital Humanities Hackathon was first organised in 2015 on a shoestring budget and very little planning. In subsequent years, DHH attracted a global audience in becoming a recognised European digital humanities event as a DARIAH and CLARIN summer school. DHH has also received international acclaim in the form of rewards.

During the hackathon's ten-year history, every year approximately 50 attendees (including ca. 40 participants, and one to three team leaders per group) and four main organisers, have been involved in the hackathon, totalling 600 people, with over 100 people from outside Finland. Risto Turunen, who participated in the hackathon for the first time in 2015, and has since become a group leader, commented that "DHH is the best thing humanists can do with their pants on". At DHH, the participants have the opportunity to receive five ECTS credits for the completion of the hackathon. The feedback on the hackathon we have received over the years has been overwhelmingly positive.

As one of the participants put it:

"The best part was the time we had to get into the topic of our research and explore the dataset. Having this time to work together on ideas, to try out things of which some worked

out and others didn't and to come to actual results was something I did not expect in the beginning. I think the length of the Hackathon is truly ideal."

Every year, team members present their work in a public event on the last day of the hackathon. The presentation materials of the groups are available online for several years, and the recorded presentations from 2019. As concrete outputs, each hackathon group has produced a poster or a report (in 2021 when the hackathon was organised as an online event) that summarises the group's work during the hackathon. The blog posts groups have written are published online. Source code, datasets, and other accompanying materials the groups have created are available on public GitHub repositories. Additionally, some student reports on the hackathon have been published.

The hackathon has proven to be a venue for catalysing further research initiatives. One such initiative was the 2017 group "The media and the political elite", and later Research Council of Finland funding was received for the FLOPO project (2019–2022). Scientific publications stemming from the hackathon include the results of the 2017 group "Categories, norms and genres – critical readings in numbers" [1], 2019 group "Newspapers and Capitalism" [2], and 2022 group "Parliamentary networks" [3]. Reflections on organising the hackathon (and digital humanities studies at the University of Helsinki in general) have been discussed in articles [4, 5].

Evidence of the Impact

[1] Agata Dominowska, Elsi Hyttinen, Peter Ivanics, Mikko Koho, Ilona Pikkanen and Risto Turunen. 2019. "Hiding in Plain Sight: Poetry in Newspapers and How to Approach it." *Human IT: Journal for Information Technology Studies as a Human Science*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 145–171, University of Borås. <https://humanit.hb.se/article/view/594/725>

[2] Ruben Ros and Sarah Oberbichler. 2020. "The Helsinki Digital Humanities Hackathon." *Twin Talks: Understanding and Facilitating Collaboration in Digital Humanities 2020*. Proceedings of the Twin Talks 2 and 3 Workshops at DHH 2020 and DH 2020: 66–74. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2717/paper07.pdf>

[3] Jure Skubic, Jan Angermeier, Alexandra Bruncrona, Bojan Evkoski and Larissa Leiminger. 2022. "Networks of Power: Gender analysis in selected European parliaments." Proceedings of the 2nd Workshop on Computational Linguistics for Political Text Analysis (CPSS-2022), Potsdam, Germany. <https://old.gscl.org/en/arbeitskreise/cpss/cpss-2022/workshop-proceedings-2022>

[4] Mikko Tolonen. 2019 "Teaching Digital Humanities at the University of Helsinki." *EuropeNow*. <https://www.europenowjournal.org/2019/09/09/teaching-digital-humanities-at-the-university-of-helsinki/>

[5] Mikko Tolonen, Eetu Mäkelä, Jani Marjanen and Tuuli Tahko. 2020. "Arvutiteaduse kaasamine humanitaarharidusse." *Methis : studia humaniora Estonica*, 21:26, 35-50. <https://doi.org/10.7592/methis.v21i26.16909>

Poster reveal party at DHH23

DHH19: Participants at the Helsinki Cathedral

c. Investing on Open Science

In 2024, we stepped up our drive towards Open Science by experiencing the Diamond Publishing model and contributing to the reform of Research Assessment (RA) with open peer review procedures and innovative and diverse research outputs that still remain out of the scope of the traditional evaluation.

A milestone in the year has been the launch of *Transformations*. *Transformations* doesn't pretend to be "just another" Digital Humanities journal but will foster above all the infrastructural integrity, sustainability and reproducibility of research practices in the arts and humanities. Over the year, we further strengthened our Open Science skills and experience through many dimensions: data sharing, management practices and Open Access policy building, in collaboration with research expert communities at European level.

1. A new Diamond publishing venue

An important action in the year was the launch of *Transformations: A DARIAH Journal*, during the DARIAH Annual Event 2024 in Lisbon. The added value of *Transformations* is to help the Arts and Humanities communities to reuse tools and workflows.

With this new innovative publishing project, DARIAH fulfils several commitments:

Support and better assess innovative forms and outputs

With its first issue on *Workflows: Digital Methods for Reproducible Research Practices in the Arts and Humanities*, we invited contributors to explore, assess, and analyse the challenges of designing, implementing, documenting and sharing digitally-enabled workflows in the context of arts and humanities research. 27 submissions were received of which 23 valid submissions are undergoing peer review.

Promote a transparent (FAIR) and ethical publishing model

Episciences, the hosting platform of *Transformations*, meets the FAIR criteria and the exemplary criteria defined by the Open Science French Steering Committee. The Episciences platform is also onboarded on OpenAIRE Graph as Data source enabling broader visibility and use for all SSH and Arts communities in Europe.

Enhance reviewing skills and contribute to transforming the Research Assessment framework

Open Peer Review enhances the quality, reliability and effectiveness of the Peer Review process by enabling open discussions among reviewers and the wider community. To be implemented for the first issue of the Journal a Scientific Committee was established with 26 members representing a wide range of expertise in the digital arts and humanities. With evaluation procedures based on open identities and the plan to make evaluation reports public, we hope to contribute to better recognition and reward of reviewers' skills and efforts.

Find out more on *Transformations* on the journal's website (<https://transformations.episciences.org/>).

TRANSFORMATIONS

A DARIAH Journal

2. Building capacity and skills on evaluating innovative outputs

The OPERAS Innovation Lab team took a bold step forward and in 2024 released the *Guidelines on Publishing and Evaluating Innovative Outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities*. Building on the Innovation Lab case studies of innovative outputs, DARIAH contributed to the OPERAS Plus project on how to recognise and reward innovation, ensuring that research excellence is no longer measured by citations alone but by real-world influence, interdisciplinary reach, and societal impact. Grounded in the principles of the DORA declaration and the CoARA agreement, this framework advocates for a broader recognition of research outputs and the crucial role of research infrastructures in supporting

innovation. Informed by the stakeholders' insights from the validation workshop "How to Support Innovation in Social Sciences and Humanities?", held in Zadar in April 2024, ten criteria for assessing innovative projects were formulated, encompassing aspects such as novelty, utility, and sustainability.

Find out more on Zenodo ([DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14221727](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14221727)).

3. Supporting OA Monographs policies at European level

This year saw the completion of the PALOMERA (Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area) project. Its main goal was to understand why so few OA policies include books, and to provide actionable recommendations.

DARIAH's involvement in the project concentrated around the data collection and analysis phases of the project while also being responsible for shaping the project's Data Management Plan. In alignment with DARIAH's Open Science and Training strategy, DARIAH significantly contributed to the Recommendations for Open Access Book Policies published by PALOMERA at the end of 2024 and in particular, to the section on researchers' recommendations.

4. Strengthening management practices through DARIAH WG's cross-collaboration

The Research Data Management and Multilingual DH WGs joined forces in 2024 in a research project financed by the DARIAH WG Funding Call 2023-2025 "Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages". In the context of this project, they organised a workshop in Hamburg in August to develop several workflows that were simultaneously published on the SSH Open Marketplace.

From an Open Science perspective, all workflows presented during the session stressed the very central position of documentation of the corpora and structure of metadata which enable findability and interoperability of corpora. Such workshops where workflows are shared and formalised are crucial to allow researchers and institutions to improve collaboration, in particular in the domain of under-resourced languages so as to increase the visibility of languages beyond English in Digital Humanities.

Find out more on the DARIAH Open blog (<https://dariahopen.hypotheses.org/>).

Building a Data Policy for the research community

One more 2024 highlight was the publication of the second version of the DARIAH Data Policy. This policy targets both data producers and data providers. It outlines the basic principles for managing and sharing research data within the DARIAH infrastructure and beyond. The policy, thus, helps institutions and researchers to be more visible in the European Digital Arts and Humanities landscape.

Grounded in the DARIAH Open Science context and guided by the main DARIAH resource types, the DARIAH Data Policy advocates for efficient data management practices promoting data sharing and collaboration within the research community and through the entire research life cycle, from project planning and standardisation to publication. Alongside the DARIAH Service Policy, and the upcoming Guidelines for handling DARIAH resources, the DARIAH Data Policy contributes to the DARIAH resources management framework of the infrastructure.

Find out more on DARIAH Data Policy v2 on the DARIAH Zenodo Library Group (<https://zenodo.org/communities/dariah/records>).

Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages' Project (Hamburg Workshop – August 2024)

d. Creating Tools and Services for the Community

In 2024, DARIAH made substantial strides in strengthening its technical infrastructure, with a special emphasis on enhancing connectivity and interoperability between data and services available in the broader landscape.

Developments include the consolidation of the SSH Open Marketplace (marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/) as a trusted central catalogue for tools and services and the successful transition of the OpenMethods metablog (openmethods.dariah.eu) to a community-led service run by DARIAH.it. 2024 was also the year in which the Unified National Reporting App, or UNR App for short, was created. Together, these initiatives highlight DARIAH's commitment to building an ecosystem that supports open, reusable, and richly contextualized digital scholarship.

Guiding principle for these infrastructural developments is that of “resource pathways” – the focus on improving the flow and propagation of information in a complex heterogeneous ecosystem comprising vast amounts of resources of different kinds (datasets, tools, services, catalogues etc.) produced and provided by many different stakeholders.

The SSH Open Marketplace as central discovery solution

The SSH Open Marketplace (SSHOMP) has established itself as a go-to solution for learning about tools and methods in the social sciences and humanities domains. With its strong governance model relying on a standing editorial board and the backing of major SSH research infrastructures, it represents a stable component of the landscape that can be reliably built upon. Consequently, it is being utilized and further developed in numerous infrastructural projects (ECHOES, OSCARS, ATRIUM, OS Trails), in line with the overall concept of “resource pathways”, i.e. propagating information between systems. For example, in the ATRIUM project the information about the project service portfolio is being maintained directly in the SSHOMP and dynamically retrieved and displayed on the ATRIUM website (<https://atrium-research.eu/services/>). This streamlined approach not only simplifies data entry for project members but also promotes interoperability through the use of a common data structure. Moreover, it enables actors from diverse institutional contexts and initiatives to contribute to a collaborative curation of shared information collection (much like the wiki model).

SSHOMP places particular emphasis on workflows

and the description of methodological approaches for accomplishing specific tasks. One of the main outputs of the ATRIUM project—workflows for handling different types of data—will be published through SSHOMP. The project also introduces specific requirements for the Marketplace, such as versioning and persistent identifiers (PIDs) for workflows, which are driving further development of the platform.

The utility of SSHOMP as a central information hub is further demonstrated by its adoption in other initiatives. For instance, Text+ uses the SSHOMP API to build its own registry of tools and services (<https://registry.text-plus.org/admin/entities/dienst/>); and DARIAH WGs, especially the Bibliodata WG, the Multilingual DH WG and the RDM WG, made a substantial contribution to the creation of SSHOMP workflows.

The SSHOMP Editorial Board actively supports these initiatives through training sessions and conference workshops. In 2024, two discussion papers have highlighted this work: *Contextualizing Research Tools & Services Through Workflows in the SSH Open Marketplace* (doi.org/10.5334/johd.192) and *Open Bibliographical Data Workflows and the Multilinguality Challenge* (doi.org/10.5334/johd.190).

Sustainability: OpenMethods metablog

With over 250 posts contributed by committed Volunteer Editors, OpenMethods metablog gives accessibility and visibility of scholarly conversations on digital methods. OpenMethods was originally launched through the Humanities at Scale project and then sustained as a DARIAH Core Service. In 2024, OpenMethods transitioned to a Community Service operated by DARIAH-IT, while the website itself is still hosted by the French DARIAH consortium. This transition demonstrates the capacity of DARIAH as a resilient network able to provide stable services to the community.

Recognising its value in showcasing digital methods and tools, DARIAH supported DARIAH-IT in taking over its daily operations, ensuring the platform's continued growth and relevance in the evolving DH landscape. Looking ahead, efforts focus on recruiting new volunteer editors, redefining editorial roles, and strengthening workflows to foster deeper community engagement.

Executable workflows and innovative publishing pathways

The *Journal of Digital History* (JDH), a Community Service from DARIAH Luxembourg, exemplifies DARIAH's mission by promoting reproducible, transparent, and narratively rich scholarly practices in the digital humanities. Published by the Luxembourg Centre for Contemporary and Digital History (C²DH) in partnership with De Gruyter, JDH delivers concrete value through its innovative approach to scholarly publishing.

As illustrated in its recent article on Time: the Cost of Reproducibility (<https://doi.org/10.1515/JDH-2025-0001?locatt=label:JDHFULL>), the journal embeds structured data and computational methods within peer-reviewed research. This model supports end-to-end reproducibility—ensuring that workflows from data collection to analysis are transparent, verifiable, and reusable. Such practices directly support DARIAH's commitment to open, sustainable, and high-quality digital scholarship.

Each JDH article is assigned a persistent identifier, safeguarding long-term access and traceability of both the publication and its underlying research components. These identifiers reinforce the integrity of the scholarly record and facilitate seamless citation and integration within broader research infrastructures.

Importantly, JDH complements the narrative workflows of the SSH Open Marketplace. While the Marketplace aggregates tools and services and documents their use in research, JDH showcases their scholarly application in executable publishing environments. Together, they exemplify how DARIAH services can bridge technical infrastructure and narrative-driven research, demonstrating the impact of interoperable and FAIR-aligned workflows in practice.

DARIAH UNR App

The DARIAH UNR App, launched as a prototype in 2024, is a significant development contributing to DARIAH's efforts in harmonising information about its resources. The UNR App aims to support National Coordinators in their annual reporting on the contributions and activities of national consortia. While this information is primarily needed for internal reporting, the goal of the UNR App is to move beyond that and make this information available to the community.

Building on the concept of "resource pathways", the application is designed to use information already available in other components as much as possible. Particularly, it reuses the collection of tools and services in the SSH Open Marketplace, and harvests it automatically for the corresponding national report. Moreover, this same information from the Marketplace is also used to populate the Tools & Services Catalogue on the DARIAH website.

The UNR application is planned to be further developed in 2025 into the **DARIAH Knowledge Base**, a central place to collaboratively curate diverse information about the DARIAH infrastructure. The DARIAH Knowledge Base is planned to feed the DARIAH website and will also be available to other DARIAH services via a public API.

e. Connecting Communities: The DARIAH Annual Event 2024

The DARIAH Annual Event 2024 in numbers:

The DARIAH Annual Event took place in Lisbon, Portugal, from 18-21 June 2024. For this event, outgoing DARIAH Director, Toma Tasovac, Chair of the Programme Committee, presented the community with the theme *Workflows: Digital Methods for Reproducible Research Practices in the Arts and Humanities*. Beyond the sharing of resources and tools, the various contributions of the Annual Event focused on the sequence of steps required to best facilitate and optimise, share, use, and re-use.

Our local hosts for 2024 were NOVA-FCSH, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, with additional organisation by the ROSSIO Infrastructure, the Portuguese node of DARIAH. A record number of diverse and engaging submissions resulted in a packed schedule of papers, panels, poster presentations and more over the Annual Event's days in Lisbon. As was the case in the last two years, the record for total attendees was once again broken, as more than 250 participants from 39 different countries were in attendance. Several (presenting) participants who attended were based outside of Europe, pointing to both the growing importance of Digital Humanities infrastructures as well as the role that DARIAH maintains within this domain.

The structure of the event followed a similar format to previous years, allowing for internal DARIAH meetings, open to the wider community, WG meetings, paper sessions, panel sessions, poster and demo sessions, plenary sessions and keynotes. The opening keynote on Wednesday, 18 June, was delivered by Meredith Martin (Centre for Digital Humanities at Princeton University) entitled 'All Worked Up About Data'. The final session of the Annual Event on Friday featured a celebratory panel with reflections on the first decade of DARIAH as well as the announcement of the launch of *Transformations*:

A DARIAH Journal. The Annual Event 2024 closed with a warm send-off to Toma Tasovac, as one of his last responsibilities as a DARIAH Director, was to Co-Chair the Annual Event.

For more information check the DARIAH AE 2024 Book of Abstracts (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13655424>).

Pictures were kindly provided by Ralitsa Ivanova, CC BY

3. Doing things right and doing the right things

a. Changes in the Organisation

2024 saw significant changes in the DARIAH-EU Board of Directors. Toma Tasovac's second term of office as DARIAH-EU Director and President of the Board ended on 31 August. He was succeeded in his role as President of the Board by Agiatis Benardou. Susan Schreibman was appointed Director by the General Assembly in June 2024 while she officially joined the Board from 1 September. Since then, DARIAH's Board has been composed of Agiatis Benardou, Sally Chambers and Susan Schreibman. It should be noted that Toma Tasovac continues to support DARIAH-EU as Strategic Advisor to the Board alongside his role as Principal Investigator on the EU project ATRIUM.

2024 saw a significant recruitment drive at the DARIAH Coordination Office, following the increased number of European projects in which DARIAH is involved. Megan Black was hired on 1 January as Project Manager of ATRIUM. Amelia McConville, who replaced Eliza Papaki during her parental leave, was recruited as Community Engagement Officer on 11 March. Anne Baillot joined the team as Research Fellow on 15 April. Finally, Michael Kurzmeier started his work as Technical Officer on 1 November.

While there were no changes in the Joint Research Committee in 2024, the Scientific Board welcomed four new members in November: Claire Warwick, Elena Pierazzo, Isto Huvila and Salvatore Capasso.

b. Measuring our impact

Each year, DARIAH collects a set of quantitative and qualitative indicators which capture our achievements, measure the organisation's development, and demonstrate the depth and richness of DARIAH's value and impact.

DARIAH's current set of KPIs is composed of 10 quantitative indicators across three high-level categories - Usage, Effectiveness, Impact - and is based on data collected from our national consortia and at European and international level. These quantitative indicators are complemented with the annual DARIAH Impact Case Studies as their qualitative counterpart.

Three Impact Case Studies were also produced for the year 2024:

- [Building a Human Network for Sustainable Digital Humanities in Croatia](#) (pages 14-15)
- [Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure \(CLS INFRA\)](#) (pages 20-21)
- [Helsinki Digital Humanities Hackathon](#) (pages 26-27)

In this section, we aim to provide our stakeholders with an accurate picture of the performance and impact of DARIAH at a European scale for the year 2024. We are committed to the ongoing improvement of our methodology and data collection process; These updates are made in good faith to enhance reliability, though we acknowledge that such improvements can occasionally impact year-over-year comparability.

USAGE

In 2024, the number of DARIAH member countries remained constant with 22 members, however we regretted Denmark's departure at the end of the year.

The expansion of our national consortia is evidenced by a steady rise in partner institutions, growing from 306 in 2023 to 324 in 2024, and a notable 34% surge in contributors. This growth underscores the increasing dynamism and reach of the national consortia.

The momentum of the DARIAH community is evidenced by a 43% increase in audience participation and a record 2,678 events organized across the consortia in 2024. This trajectory confirms a heightened level of awareness and active involvement within the Digital Humanities European landscape compared to 2023.

At the end of 2024, 234 training materials were available on the platform DARIAH-Campus, reflecting the growing richness and diversity of the training offer.

While the number of services offered across national and European platforms rose significantly, from 294 to 359, recorded platform interactions decreased to 172 million in 2024. This divergence primarily reflects technical tracking limitations and data collection gaps rather than a decline in actual user engagement.

IMPACT

In terms of impact, the number of publications increased significantly (+46%) illustrating the growing production of knowledge thanks to the services and tools offered by the infrastructure.

Funding leveraged at both national and European levels remained robust in 2024, totaling €55.8 million. This sustained investment underscores the ability of national consortia to secure large-scale project funding and reflects the deep, continuous commitment of our member countries to the Digital Humanities.

EFFECTIVENESS

The third DARIAH Strategic Action Plan, which officially started on 01.06.2022 for a total duration of 3 years, is composed of 13 high-level goals.

On 31 December 2024, we had completed 91% of it.

4. Looking Ahead

As DARIAH's network has grown, so has its ambitions to provide the services, tools, and expertise necessary for conducting and publishing humanities research in computationally-mediated and intensive ways. Through funded research, such as OSCARS and ATRIUM, and its collaboration with other SSH infrastructures through the SSH Open Marketplace, it will continue to provide services, workshops, online training content, and mentoring to researchers throughout the European Research Area. DARIAH's involvement in other European projects, such as ECHOES, serves to keep DARIAH at the centre of European developments in research infrastructures in the digital humanities and heritage.

In 2024 DARIAH instituted a new monthly series, *DARIAH Spotlight*, which serves to highlight research carried out by the WGs and in Digital Humanities projects throughout Europe. The goal of this series is to make visible to the wider DARIAH community research that may only be known within the discipline within which it is created.

As digital tools and methods become more ubiquitous for humanities researchers, DARIAH is extremely well positioned to meet the challenge of training not just new generations of researchers, but more established researchers who wish to take advantage of the tools, services, datasets, and methods which are revolutionising our fields, the questions we can ask of our data, and the remediation and remaking of the objects of our contemplation.

DARIAH Annual Event 2024, picture kindly provided by Fabian Fess, CC BY

The image features a dark blue background with a central white text element. Surrounding the text are several concentric, curved lines in various colors including orange, purple, blue, green, pink, and yellow. These lines are of varying thicknesses and are punctuated with small, solid-colored circles of the same hue. The overall composition is dynamic and modern, suggesting a digital or technological theme.

Appendices

Appendix I: Administrative and Legal Details

Who's who in DARIAH

Body: Board of Directors

Agiatis Benardou

Digital Curation Unit, IMSI, ATHENA R.C./ Athens University of Economics and Business

Sally Chambers

Ghent University

Susan Schreibman

Maastricht University

Body: Scientific Board

Panos Constantopoulos	Chair of the DARIAH Scientific Board, Athens University of Economics and Business
Payal Arora	Erasmus University Rotterdam
Marko Demantowsky	University of Vienna
Martine Denoyelle	Institut National de l'Histoire de l'Art
Milena Dobрева	GATE Institute
Alain Heureux	Virtuology Academy
Sarah Kenderine	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
Andrew Perkis	NTNU ARTEC

* Shaded area marks colleagues that left DARIAH before the end of 2024

Body: Joint Research Committee

Andrea Scharnhorst	Chief Integration Officer	DARIAH / DANS
Tibor Kálmán	Heads of VCC1	GWDG
Tomasz Parkola		Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center
Maria Ilvanidou	Heads of VCC2	Digital Curation Unit, IMSI, ATHENA R.C.
Tanja Wissik		ACDH-CH
Georgios Artopoulos	Heads of VCC3	STARC, Cyprus Institute
Elena Gigliarelli		CNR National Research Council Italy
Adeline Joffres	Heads of VCC4	TGIR Huma-Num (CNRS)
Carmen Di Meo		OVI-CNR institute
Tomasz Umerle	Member of the JRC	Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences

Body: DARIAH Coordination Office			
	Anne Grésillon Chief Organisation Officer		
	Michael Kurzmeier Technical Officer		
	Amelia McConville Community Engagement Officer		
	Eliza Papaki Outreach and Communications Officer		
	Marco Raciti European Project Manager		
	Simon Saldner Integration Officer		
	Andrea Scharnhorst Chief Integration Officer		
	Toma Tasovac Strategic Advisor to the Board of Directors		
	Edward J. Gray National Coordination Officer		

Body: National Coordinators Committee		
Nanette Rißler-Pipka	Chair of NCC / Germany	Göttingen State and University Library
Martin Lhoták	Vice Chair of NCC / Czech Republic	Czech Academy of Sciences
Walter Scholger	Austria	Center for Information Modeling – Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities, University of Graz
Tanja Wissik (Deputy)	Austria	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage, Austrian Academy of Sciences
Christophe Verbruggen	Belgium	Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities
Lana Šehović	Bosnia and Herzegovina	University of Sarajevo
Dimitar Iliev	Bulgaria	Sofia University
Kiril Simov	Bulgaria	Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
Koraljka Kuzman Šlogar	Croatia	Archive, Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research
Marinos Ioannides	Cyprus	Cyprus University of Technology
Kristoffer Laigaard Nielbo	Denmark	Aarhus University
Nicolas Larousse	France	Huma-Num
Daniel Kurzawe (Deputy)	Germany	University of Göttingen
Paris Potiropoulos	Greece	Academy of Athens
Jennifer Edmond	Ireland	Trinity College Dublin
Nicole Basaraba (Deputy)	Ireland	Trinity College Dublin
Emiliano Degl'Innocenti	Italy	National Research Council of Italy (CNR)
Alessia Spadi (Deputy)	Italy	National Research Council of Italy (CNR)
Tugce Karatas	Luxembourg	Luxembourg Centre for Contemporary and Digital History
Claudia Borg	Malta	University of Malta
Richard Zijdeman	Netherlands	International Institute of Social History (IISH)
Karolina Brylska	Poland	University of Warsaw
Amelia Aguiar Andrade	Portugal	NOVA FCSH
Daniel Alves (Deputy)	Portugal	NOVA FCSH
Snežana Petrović	Serbia	Serbian Academy for Sciences and Arts
German Rigau Claramunt	Spain	HiTZ, Basque Center for Language Technology
Vojko Gorjanc	Slovenia	University of Ljubljana
Koraljka Golub	Sweden	Linnaeus University
Rita Gautschy	Switzerland	Swiss National Data & Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH)
Cristina Grisot (Deputy)	Switzerland	Swiss National Data & Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH)

Appendix II: Finances

1) DARIAH ERIC

a) Preliminary remarks

It should be noted that, at the time of writing this annual report, the accounts of DARIAH ERIC for the year 2024 have not yet been audited. DARIAH's General Assembly traditionally reviews the auditor's report and decides on the financial statements at its November 2025 meeting. It should be nonetheless mentioned that the last report of the auditor in 2023 concluded that DARIAH's financial statements "give a true and fair view of the assets and liabilities, and of the financial position of the organisation on December 31, 2023 and of the results of its operation in accordance with the accounting rules and principles applicable in France."

However, this does not preclude us from already giving an accurate situation of DARIAH's finances for the year 2024 that reflect its operations in an understandable and transparent manner for its stakeholders.

It is important to clarify that, in this first section "DARIAH ERIC", only the resources and expenses related to DARIAH's core activities – i.e., without its participation in European projects – are accounted for. Besides, due to their very nature, the in-kind contributions are not included in the calculation of resources available to run DARIAH's operations.

b) Resources and financial overview

22 member countries contributed to DARIAH ERIC's budget 2024 in two different ways: through cash and in-kind contributions. In accordance with the budget voted by the General Assembly, the contributions from the member countries amounted to:

2024 total cash contribution	948 250 €
2024 total in-kind contribution	5 693 053 €

The total income 2024 is mostly composed of cash contributions from member countries and overheads of European projects that have been completed and paid in full. In 2022, this applied to the projects EOSC-Future (Project number 101017536) and PALOMERA (Project number 101094270), completed in March and December 2024 respectively. Moreover, the financial support of CLARIN and CESSDA for the development of the SSH Open Marketplace, as well as the participation of DARIAH to the Common Data Space for Cultural Heritage led by the Europeana Foundation, contributed to DARIAH's total revenue in the year 2024.

With a total income of 1.035.048 € and a total expense of 1.011.409 €, DARIAH's balance for the year 2024 is as follows:

DARIAH balance 2023	827 669 €
DARIAH income 2024	1 035 048 €
DARIAH expenses 2024	1 011 409 €
Balance 2024	23 638 €
Total balance	851 307 €

c) Focus on the expenses

In 2024, the operational costs are distributed as follows:

Type of costs – DARIAH only	2023
Personnel costs	691,439 €
Travel and accommodation	62,421 €
Community support through project funding	48,228 €
Core services	39,327 €
Rent	36,348 €
Catering	35,612 €
Training material	25,959 €
Membership in EU organisations	20,900 €
Communication	14,818 €
Accounting and audit	13,783 €
Financial support to partner events	9,867 €
Equipment	5,023 €
Bank charges	2,547 €
Consulting	1,235 €
Cooperating Partners	950 €
Internal training	919 €
Conference fees	770 €
Consumables	695 €
Publication	567 €
Total	1,011,409 €

Personnel remains the largest component of DARIAH's operational costs, representing 68,4% of the total budget. The second largest expenditure is travel and accommodation (6,2%), reflecting a high level of activity in 2024; this included numerous representation efforts and events, most notably the DARIAH Annual Event in Lisbon. Financial support to research communities, specifically tailored project funding for arts and humanities scholars via the DARIAH Theme and Working Group calls, ranks third at 4,8%. Finally, core services account for 3,9% of costs, primarily directed toward the maintenance and development of the SSH Open Marketplace, alongside essential communication infrastructure such as Zoom, Google Workspace, and Basecamp.

It is interesting to mention that the item "Membership in EU organisations" refers to fees paid to be part of the EOSC association, the OPERAS infrastructure or the European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities (EASSH). It may be also useful to clarify that under the heading "financial support to partner events" (1%) reference is made to DARIAH's financial contribution to the organisation of the Helsinki Digital Humanities Hackathon and the European Summer University in Digital Humanities 2024 in Romania.

d) Focus on personnel costs

Although personnel costs are the largest item of expenditure, this does not reflect an excessive administration but rather a strong and diverse team that works directly to support the research communities and meet their needs in terms of communication, research policy, service development, etc. It should be noted that the above-mentioned personnel costs do not take into account the work carried out in the framework of the European projects. Below is the composition of the DARIAH central team:

Staff Costs – administration	FTE
Directors	1,5
Secretary-General	1
Legal and administration officer	0,8
European project manager	0,9
ATRIUM project manager	1

Staff Costs – support for the community	FTE
Outreach and communications officer	1
Chief technology officer	0,5
Officer for service development	1
Open Science officer	1
Working group coordinators and experts for in-kind contributions	0,8
Officer for national coordination	0,6
Training and education officer	0,8
Community engagement officer	0,8
Research fellow	0,5
Technical officer	0,2

2) European projects

a) Financial overview

DARIAH's participation in several European projects requires a specific financial monitoring according to the rules set up by the European Commission. Consequently, the resources and expenses related to EU projects are accounted for separately for transparency purposes.

In 2024, DARIAH was involved in the following projects:

- Advancing FronTier Research In the Arts and hUManities (ATRIUM), Project number 101132163
- EOSC future (EOSC Future), Project number 101017536
- Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure (CLS INFRA), Project number 101004984
- On the road to sustainability: paving the way for OPERAS as an efficient open Social Sciences and Humanities scholarly communication Research Infrastructure (OPERAS-PLUS), Project number 101079608
- PALOMERA – Policy Alignment of Open access Monographs in the European Research Area (PALOMERA), Project number 101094270
- The Second implementation project for the ERIC Forum (ERIC Forum 2), Project number 101124559
- OSCARS - Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society, Project number 101129751
- European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science (ECHOES), Project number 101157364
- Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked interdisciplinary Exploration (TRIPLE), Grant agreement number 863420
- Authentication and Authorisation for Research Collaboration Technical Revision to Enhance Effectiveness (AARC TREE), Project number 101131237

In 2024, the operational costs related to European projects are distributed as follows:

Breakdown by project	Credit	Debit
AARC-TREE	4 099 €	4 099 €
ATRIUM	229 043 €	229 043 €
CLS Infra	28 337 €	28 337 €
ECHOES	16 244 €	16 244 €
EOSC Future	7 584 €	7 584 €
ERIC Forum 2	23 032 €	23 032 €
OPERAS-Plus	26 782 €	26 782 €
OSCARS	31 038 €	31 038 €
PALOMERA	44 267 €	44 267 €
TRIPLE	946 €	946 €
Total European projects	411 371 €	411 371 €

Breakdown by type of costs	2024
Personnel costs	386 298 €
Communication	9 486 €
Travel and accommodation	8 170 €
Catering	7 228 €
Consumables	189 €
Total	411 371 €

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